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TECHNOLOGICAL AND EXTENSION GAPS AND STRATEGIES FOR AGRO ECONOMIC SITUATIONS (AES) IN MAHABUBNAGAR DISTRICT OF TELANGANA STATE

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Abstract:

Climate is an important factor of the geographical distribution and productivity of vegetation. Therefore, the climatic changes have insightful implications for rural livelihoods, in so particular to the soil and water resources. Global climate change will increase the stress on agricultural systems by potentially decreasing yields at the very time when demand for food is growing dramatically. Like hunger, the stresses that arise from rapid climate change will fall most heavily on the poorest, the most vulnerable, and those least able to adopt new technology.

Although increases in average temperature worldwide are the most predictable consequence of greenhouse gas emissions, many other aspects of global and regional climate will also change. Some of these changes will be much more significant than others, with respect to agricultural output. The effects include, increased growing season, extended margin of the potential cropping and grazing in mid-latitude regions, which may reduce the yield potential in core areas of current production as increased temperatures encourage more rapid maturation of plants and shorten the period of grain filling and extended geographic range of some insect pests. The effects also include, changes in crop types, irrigation management, fertilizer use, soil drainage and erosion and farm infrastructure. In this circumstance a study on Technological and Extension Gaps and Strategies for Agro Economic Situations in Mahabubnagar district in Telangana state with respect to climate change has been conducted.

Key Words: Agro Economic Situations (AES), Farming systems, Extension Gaps, Strategies, etc

Introduction

Developing countries like India are considered particularly vulnerable to climatic changes due to their dependency on climate sensitive sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, forestry, water and other natural resources and limited capacities to anticipate and respond to climate changes. Most of the Indian population is concentrated in rural areas, which are harsh climatic regions of mountains, deserts, and river deltas, which make them more susceptible to changing climate. However, 62% of the cropped area is still dependent on rainfall, a component of climate.

The climatic variations in India have huge effect, as the agriculture sector in the country. Over 60 per cent of the crop area is under rain-fed agriculture that is highly vulnerable to climate variability and change. In Mahabubnagar district characterized by hot summers with low rainfall and relatively moderate winters. The average rainfall of Mahabubnagar district is 604 mm, most of it received during south west monsoon period (June – September). The rainfall is scanty and erratic resulting in generally hot climate. Seasonal rainfall distribution indicates that Mahabubnagar with low precipitation from the northeast monsoon is more drought-prone in the later part of crop-growing season. About three-fourth of the mandals in the district have rainfall of less than 600 mm.

Objectives

The objective of the study is to identify the Technological and Extension Gaps and to develop Strategies for Agro Economic Situations. This analysis would further help to make suitable proposals for action.

Methodology

Mahabubnagar district in Telangana state was selected for the present study. As a part of the study, three representative villages of AES II, VII and X viz., Masthipur, Mulamalla and Komireddypally respectively selected randomly and were critically analyzed to find the research and extension gaps in the district. In these three villages data was collected from the villagers through participatory methodology by using PRA tools and focused group discussion with the village elders. The data was analyzed and presented below with suitable research and extension strategies for these situations.

Findings

Distribution of villagers based on resources available

The information furnished in the Table 1 given below clearly indicates that majority of the farming families in the district were resource poor with an aggregate of 70 per cent in all the three AES.

- **Table 1: Distribution of villagers based on resources available**

S. No	Type of Families	AES II		AES VII		AES X	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
01	Resource Rich	50	17.00	150	37.50	70	17.50
02	Resource Poor	250	83.00	250	62.50	330	82.50

- **Existing Farming systems in the AES**
- An attempt was made to understand the existing farming situations in the three AES. The existing farming systems greatly vary with the situation to situation. The first two AES i.e., AES II and VII have water source from PJP canal. Hence, Paddy was cultivated in 50 per cent of the area. The X situation that constitutes about 70% of the district is characterized by Paddy/ Castor followed by Fallow. This was due the lack of irrigation facilities in this situation. But, few farmers in this situation were getting more income horticultural and floricultural crops.
- **Table 2: Existing Farming systems in the AES**

S. No	Existing Farming System	AES II		AES VII		AES X	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
01	Fallow – Groundnut	270	90.00	40	10.00	-	0.00
02	Paddy – Paddy	45	15.00	360	90.00	-	0.00
03	Paddy – Fallow	90	30.00	-	0.00	160	40.00
04	Castor – Fallow	-	0.00	08	2.00	160	40.00
05	Horticulture	-	0.00	08	2.00	04	1.00
06	Groundnut – Fallow	-	0.00	-	0.00	08	2.00
07	Sunflower – Fallow	-	0.00	-	0.00	10	2.50

Incomes from Farming Systems

Figures presented in Table 3 show that horticulture proved as the successful farming systems with a net income of Rs. 20,000 and 40,000 in AES VII and AES X respectively. The figures suggest that Agri-Horti farming system would be more profitable to the farmers in these two situations. The Table also indicates that Paddy had the low returns when compared to other crops or farming systems.

Table 3: Incomes from Farming Systems

S. No	Existing Farming System	AES II	AES VII	AES X
		Net Income in Rs. Per acre	Net Income in Rs. Per acre	Net Income in Rs Per acre
01	Fallow – Groundnut	3,000	5,000	-
02	Paddy – Paddy	2,500	2,000	-
03	Paddy – Fallow	1,000-1,500	1,000-2,000	1,000
04	Castor – Fallow	-	3,000	2,000
05	Horticulture	-	40,000	20,000
06	Groundnut – Fallow	-	-	3,000
07	Sunflower – Fallow	-	-	1,500

Trends in Farming Systems

AES II: During 1990s when the predominant farming system was Groundnut – Jowar/ Redgram in AES II, farmers in this situation had problem of wild boar, loss of fertility in soils due to mono cropping and huge investments which eventually led to reduced yields and in turn change in farming systems to Castor – Fallow due to lack of water availability in the second season. This farming situation was viable for a short period and the farmers adopted Paddy – Paddy as the water sources have increased.

AES VII: In the early 90s farming systems were predominantly based on food crops. In the mid-90s shifted to Groundnut – Fallow or Castor – Fallow. There was shift in the farming system due to commercialization. Farmers in this situation were forced to adopt Paddy – Paddy as the lands in this situation were low lying and had water logging suffered with condition.

AES X: This situation had different farming systems compared to the other two AES. In early 90s farmers used to cultivate the millets like Bajra/Jowar and a pulse crop, Redgram, as these were the predominant food grains consumed at that point of time.

The farming systems were also modified according to the change in the food habits of the people to Paddy – Fallow. Farmers were also tried Castor – Fallow farming system but could not continue to the problems like Botrytis and untimely rains. The present farming system in this situation is Paddy – Fallow.

Table 4 Trends in Farming Systems

S. No	AES	Trend of Farming Systems			
		1990	1995	2000	2005
01	II	Groundnut – Jowar/ Redgram	Groundnut – Paddy	Castor – Fallow	Paddy – Paddy Fallow – Groundnut
02	VII	Jowar/ Bajra/ Greengram/ Korra/ Redgram	Groundnut – Fallow Castor - Fallow	Paddy – Groundnut	Paddy – Paddy
03	X	Jowar/ Redgram/ Bajra	Paddy – Fallow	Castor – Fallow	Paddy – Fallow Sunflower – Fallow Castor – Fallow

Factors affecting the Farming Systems

Table given below indicates the factors and their effect on changing farming systems. It was apparent from the Table 5 availability of irrigation water, better transport facilities and selling and purchasing of the land high effect on farming systems in AES II. Shortage of labour, reduction in fodder availability and availability of irrigation water had high impact on farming systems in AES VII. In contrast, only irrigation water availability i.e., drought conditions had great effect in AES X farming systems.

Table 5 Factors affecting the Farming Systems

S. No	Type of Changing Scenario	AES II	AES VII	AES X
01	Migration of People to Urban areas	L	M	M
02	Lack of animal draught power	M	M	L
03	Increase in farm machinery	L	M	L
04	Shortage of labour	M	H	M
05	Reduction in availability of fodder	H	H	M
06	Increase in number of unemployed youth	L	L	L
07	Increase in level of education	L	L	L
08	Availability of irrigation water	H	H	H
09	Increase in rural indebtedness	M	M	M
10	Better transport facilities	H	L	L
11	Marketing facilities in the village	M	M	L
12	Selling and purchasing lands	H	M	L

H: High, M: Medium, L: Low

Livestock possession

Among various livestock animals, cattle and sheep were common in all AES in different relative proportions, wherein the purpose changed from commercial to personal use. The trends in population and productivity of milch animals were studied and found that there was decrease in the livestock population due unavailability of fodder and labour. Sheep were mainly grown on commercial basis and used for meat purpose. (Table 6)

Table 6: Livestock possession

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S. No	• Type of Livestock	AES II No.	AES VII No.	AES X No.
01	Cattle	325	60	200
02	Sheep	30	50	25-30

Constraints and problems

Mono cropping of rice was predominant followed by Rice-Rice. There were single cropped wetlands where only one crop of rice was grown in a year. The district receives rainfall from the Southwest monsoons. There was a need to develop a profitable, efficient and sustainable rice based cropping system to increase the cropping intensity as well as the farm income of the farmers.

Though resistant varieties were developed for one or two pests, multiple resistant varieties are to be developed as the pest menace is increasing day by day. Ignorance of the farmers in controlling the pests led to the non-judicious application of pesticides became major problem. Varieties, which suits for late sowing should be promoted in this area as farmers are going for late sowing because of erratic rainfall.

Excess use of irrigation water, drainage impedance, micronutrient disorders, soil problems like salinity, alkalinity, and moisture stress at critical stages of crop growth and rodent problems are quite common problems in the district which play major role in decreasing the yields of the crops.

An imbalanced use of NPK fertilizer especially excessive use of Nitrogen was the most common practice of the farmers in the district. Application of organic manure to the fields has become out dated due to many reasons apart from non-availability. There is a need to take up research on efficient nutrient management under different soils / water logged conditions / semidry / rain fed situations.

Research efforts are also required in developing improved production technology for the less favourable situations like rain fed rice and rice under water logged conditions. Strengthening of the efforts on the development, testing and popularization of farm machinery especially harvesters, threshers and driers should be made. Above all, research and extension efforts are to be focused towards development of sustainable, profitable, and stable farming systems depending upon the local conditions.

Technological gaps identified

- Lack of rice varieties that suits in waterlogged conditions and for late sowing.
- Lack of "Rice-Hybrids" suitable for different farming situations
- Non availability of good quality seed in sufficient quantities
- Lack of profitable, sustainable and efficient rice based cropping system
- Lack of production technology that reduces the cost of cultivation.
- Lack of efficient and low cost weed management practices
- Lack of profitable and sustainable farming systems that increase the farm income and economic standards of the farmers
- Lack of efficient integrated pest management technology.
- Lack of efficient and inexpensive bio control methods that can be implemented at farmers level
- Lack development of production technology of bio-control agents at farmers level
- Lack of proper research in microclimate that affects the crops.

Extension gaps:

- Lack of training to farmers in producing quality seeds in their own fields which leads to self-sufficiency in seeds thus decreasing the seed problem and increasing the farm production
- Strengthening of soil testing laboratories / soil test based recommendations and creating awareness in farmers about soil testing etc
- Popularization of "Integrated Nutrient Management" Practices
- Popularization of " Integrated Pest Management' Practices
- Creating awareness in the farmers about the benefits of increasing cropping intensity, using organic fertilizers, growing green manure crops, quality and quantity of nutrients in inorganic fertilizers and judicious use of fertilizers and pesticides
- Creating awareness among farmers about the crop climate relationship.

PROPOSED EXTENSION STRATEGIES

After analyzing the situations following extension strategies are proposed based on the data available and the experiences of the farmers. On the basis of the analysis of issues, problems, opportunities of threats, a relevant and feasible strategy has been worked out for carrying out the extension activities.

S. No	Proposed Extension Strategy	AES II	AES VII	AES X
01	Improving productivity and income of enterprises	Y (Yes)	Y (Yes)	Y (Yes)
02	Promoting vermicompost units	Y	Y	Y
03	Diversifying crops and crop rotation	Y	Y	Y
• Paddy				
01	Supply of sufficient quantities of suitable seed varieties and avoid spurious seed from private agencies	Y	Y	Y
02	Promoting INM in paddy	Y	Y	Y
03	Promotion of Integrated pest and disease management in paddy	Y	Y	Y
04	Educating farmers to use Zinc Sulphate as basal dose	Y	Y	Y
05	Promoting SRI cultivation for effective use of available water resources	-	-	Y
• Groundnut				
01	Promotion of new high yielding short duration varieties	Y	Y	Y
02	Promotion of balanced use of chemical fertilizers and INM practices	Y	Y	Y
03	Promoting the precautionary measures to the problem of untimely rains	Y	Y	Y
• Sunflower				
01	Educating farmers about recommended doses of fertilizers	-	-	Y
02	Educating the farmers about hand pollination by rubbing with a cloth on flower head	-	-	Y
• Castor				
01	Promoting resistant varieties to withstand botrytis disease	-	Y	Y
02	IPM practices to control castor semi looper	-	Y	Y
• Horticulture				
01	Promotion of floriculture like Jasmine	-	-	Y
02	Dry land horticulture in waste land and backyards	-	-	Y
03	Promotion of fruit crops like Mango and Sweet lime	Y	Y	-
04	Introduction of vegetables	Y	Y	Y
• Animal Husbandry				
01	Educating the farmers on the significance of subsidiary income	Y	Y	Y
02	Creating awareness on inclusion of balanced diet to increase productivity	Y	Y	Y
03	Convincing the farmers to follow proper preventive health care	Y	Y	Y
04	Indicating the farmers on improved fodder crops on perennial fodder varieties	Y	Y	Y
• Sheep				
01	Educating farmers on breed improvement	Y	Y	Y
02	Educating farmers on supplementing the grazing concentrate feeding	Y	Y	Y
03	Educating on proper vaccination schedule	Y	Y	Y
• Water				
01	Construction of water harvesting structures on contributory basis	-	-	Y
02	Irrigation water management in command area	Y	Y	-
03	Rain water management	-	-	Y
04	Erosion control measures to protect top soil	Y	Y	Y
05	Improvement of grass pasture land and their management with the involvement of community	Y	Y	Y
06	Water Budgeting	Y	Y	Y

Limitations

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Present study has been conducted only in a few blocks of Mahabubnagar district and the information is based on primary and secondary data. This research could have been more authenticated if it would have more number of sample blocks.

Conclusions

Climate is dynamic scenario. Agriculture is dependent on climate. As climate is unmanageable, coping mechanisms to the changing climate need to be developed and familiarized among farmers to evade the ill effects of climatic changes. These coping mechanisms include, late sowing, selection of short duration varieties, water conservation etc.

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